

A Knowledge-Graph for Documenting Risk of Harms in AI Systems

Delaram Golpayegani

PhD researcher, ADAPT Centre, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland, sgolpays@tcd.ie

Supervisors: Prof Dave Lewis, Dr Harshvardhan J. Pandit, Prof Declan O’Sullivan

Motivation: while Artificial Intelligence (AI) promises new and bright solutions, some serious harm could be caused by AI systems: unfairness, violation of privacy, mental health issues, to name a few. Organisations developing or utilising AI systems must be accountable to shield the stakeholders from this potential harm. AI risk management aims to minimise this harm by considering the potential negative impacts that an AI system might have on individuals, groups of people, society, etc. Maintaining and querying the information associated with risk management is essential for compliance checking, demonstrating accountability and building trust. This information usually is stored in data silos such as spreadsheets and audit logs. Utilising open data formats and standards to model the information as structured knowledge graphs would assist organisations in documenting risk of harms, performing AI risk assessment activities and accumulation of risk knowledge.

Research Objectives: the main objective of this project is to demonstrate how information pertinent to AI risk assessment can be expressed in a structured and interoperable data format to construct a knowledge graph. A key aspect of this research is in the pragmatic approach it would present for generating risk documentation required for legal compliance using the information captured in the semantic models.

Methodology: the requirements and characteristics of AI risk assessment are collected by analysing the following resources: 1) AI regulations, e.g. the EU AI Act proposal¹; 2) relevant global or European AI standards, e.g. the AI risk management standard²; 3) ethical AI guidelines, e.g. the ethics guideline for trustworthy AI³. Then, competence questions are formulated based on the requirements. Semantic Web standards, methodologies and tools are employed to create ontologies. The developed ontologies are evaluated using the competence questions and their applicability is demonstrated by applying them to a number of real-world use-cases from the AIAAIC repository⁴. This enables assessing the degree the ontologies can represent known types of AI risks. To disseminate the research, in addition to open-access publications, the ontologies are archived in a public repository, e.g. Zenodo. The research findings are also submitted to current AI standardisation activities such as CEN-CENELEC AI conformity assessment technical report preparation.

Expected Impact: organisations, researchers, authorities and any other entity involved in design, development, test, deployment, monitoring and auditing of AI systems would benefit from this work. This research would facilitate identification, management and documentation of risks associated with AI systems. It also provides a structure for generating technical documentation required for legal compliance. This work would enable organisations to communicate risk information with other entities in the AI value chain and respond to external queries such as information requests from authorities concerning conformity assessment. A potential application of the developed ontologies is annotating real-world AI incidents. This helps with classification, collation and comparison of AI risks and risk assessment activities over time and is a valuable input to the ongoing AI regulation activities and AI standardisation efforts undertaken by ISO and CEN-CENELEC.

Progress to Date: so far, the *AI Risk Ontology (AIRO)* has been developed based on the information requirements identified from the EU AI Act proposal and the draft AI risk management standard. The ontology has been applied to use-cases from the AIAAIC corpus including incidents caused by facial recognition systems, algorithms to generate knowledge graphs and autonomous cars. In addition, a systematic comparison of the EU ethical AI guideline with an AI management system (AIMS) standard was conducted to explore the extent activities recommended by the guideline address AIMS processes⁵. Furthermore, in collaboration with researchers across PROTECT ITN network⁶ an ontology for assessing trustworthy AI⁷ has been developed which captures evidence of ethical AI implementation and enables legal and ethical risk assessment. In terms of the next steps, AIRO will be extended to represent known categories of AI risk. Moreover, an ontology to express activities, artefacts and roles involved in AI risk management will be developed.

¹ European Commission, Proposal for an Artificial Intelligence Act (COM(2021) 206 final).

² ISO/IEC 23894: Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Risk management.

³ European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/177365>.

⁴ <https://www.aiaaic.org/aiaaic-repository>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/4705370>

⁶ <https://protect-network.eu/>

⁷ <https://protect.oeg.fi.upm.es/def/otaia/index-en.html>